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Possibilities of Prognosis of Sportsmen Reaction on Intensive Loading upon the Data of Computer Electrocardiography

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Abstract

Introduction. While examining the body under the influence of various factors, a need often arises to predict changes in functional supply of different body systems to optimize the value of the current impact factor. In sports medicine, the problem is related to a balanced state of an athlete, and the need to prevent the development of abnormal and pathological conditions often occurring in athletes.

Objective. To determine the prognostic criteria of a comprehensive examination of athletes concerning atypical reactions to the training load.

Methods. The examination included a study of parameters of physical development by standard methods, registration of indicators of cardiorespiratory system using Spiroartery cardiorhythmography and tests with standard physical load. Baroreflex sensitivity (BRS) indicator was defined by means of spectral method. Statistical analysis was performed using nonparametric methods of determining Mann-Whitney criteria.

Analysis of results and discussion. After examination of 32 top athletes (males, water polo) aged 20.6 ± 3.0 , we studied the effect of two-hour training load aimed at developing speed endurance and took place in the pool.

After analyzing individual changes of heart rate variability (HRV) parameters under the influence of training loads our attention was drawn to changes in HF component of HRV, the value of which in 58.1% of athletes decreased below 265.7 ms^2 , and in some athletes (38.7%) were within the standard population values ($835.3\text{-}3481.0 \text{ ms}^2$). The results led us to form two groups: the first group (examined group 1 – EG₁): 17 athletes with standard response, and the second (examined group 2 – EG₂): 15 athletes with atypical response.

Hypo kinetic type of hemodynamic is observed in 64% of athletes with atypical reaction to stress and in 88.2% of athletes with typical reaction. According to the parameters of central hemodynamic, describing the size of the left ventricle in EG₂, significantly greater ($p < 0.01$) is the end-diastolic volume and end-systolic volume than in EG₁. However, it should be noted that the rate of α -factor that characterizes the BRS and predicts the effectiveness of the regulation of cardiac pump function was significantly higher ($p < 0.01$) in EG₂.

The results of the examination of responses of athletes with atypical response to standard load showed significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) values of SBP and PBP in the initial state than in EG₁, respectively, at almost the same value of HR and DBP. The groups did not differ in terms of the period of HR recovery, however, in case of atypical response more substantial ($p < 0.05$) increase in SBP was observed as a reaction to a standard load in EG₁, as well as a slow recovery of blood pressure within 3 minutes after physical load.

Thus, the results of a complex examination of athletes allow to predict the variant of response to intense training load.

Keywords: Athletes, Prognostic criteria